

Instrument 4 (Assessment)

Name: _____ Date: _____
 Course: _____ Enrollment: _____

In the proposed ERDSL solution, using a textual approach, it is possible to represent explicitly / implicitly eight of the constructors provided for in ER modeling. Regarding the representation of these builders, evaluate:

	Disagree	Agree						
1. The entities can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	2	3	4	5	6			
2. The referential/nominative attributes can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	2	3	4	5	6			
3. The descriptive attributes can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	2	3	4	5	6			
4. The binary relations can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	2	3	4	5	6			
5. The ternary relations can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
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6. The self-relationships can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	2	3	4	5	6			
7. The cardinalities can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
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8. The generalizations/specializations can be properly represented.	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	
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